

Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan for ASPECT

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* **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

** **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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Executive Summary

This document presents the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) for ASPECT, which outlines the planned activities aiming to maximise the reach and impact of the project and its achievements. The CDEP is designed for external engagement.

The CDEP outlines the aims of CDE actions, the main target audiences, the specific activities that will be carried out during the project's lifetime and the purpose of these activities. The communication channels, website, social media strategy, and other practical information, such as visual identity, are also detailed in this document.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To provide a diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing methods enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1 Introduction

ASPECT aims to improve the provision of seamless climate information for a time horizon of up to the next 30 years, particularly aimed at different sectors, to help improve climate resilience across Europe. The pioneering scientific developments in seasonal to decadal (S2D) forecasts are essential to develop such capabilities, while it is also crucial to ensure that this information is translated in a way that is useful, usable and accessible for stakeholders. The success of the research project not only depends on the results, but also on successful communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) to maximise the project reach and impact.

ASPECT is a user-oriented project, and thus effective CDE is crucial to reach and engage users of climate information throughout the project's lifetime. A successful CDE strategy will facilitate a pathway to impact, enabling a legacy for the critical research developed in ASPECT to support adaptation decision making in Europe.

For climate information to be valuable for adaptation decisions, it must ultimately be accessible, understandable and actionable. To ensure this, the communication and dissemination activities aim to reach a wide range of stakeholders, and translate the research and results of the project into useful and usable information. In addition, these activities will support the assessment of user needs conducted in other work packages (WPs), in particular WP4 (Co-developing case studies with superusers and exploring the benefits) and WP5 (Increasing the usability of S2D climate information for adaptation). Finally, exploitation activities will ensure the legacy of the project beyond its lifetime.

This deliverable outlines the aims of CDE actions, the main target audiences, the specific activities that will be carried out during the project's lifetime and the purpose of these activities. The communication channels, website, social media strategy, and other practical information, such as visual identity, are also detailed in this document.

It should be noted that this deliverable presents a preliminary plan of activities, which will be adapted as the project progresses according to the project needs. Evaluation of the impact of activities and updates to the CDEP will be provided in upcoming deliverables (Deliverable 7.2 in month 18, D7.5 in M36, and D7.6 in M47).

1.1 Aim of the CDE plan

This document focuses on the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities carried out in ASPECT. The key objectives are to:

- Raise awareness about the project and maximise its impact
- Disseminate its results and new capabilities
- Reach and engage a wider range of audiences
- Facilitate engagement with the user communities (carried out in WP4 and WP5) through tailored, sector-specific material
- Exploit the project developments and capabilities
- Build synergies with other projects and initiatives to exchange knowledge.

1.2 Definitions and aims of CDE

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation have been defined below with the specific purpose of ASPECT in mind, which includes the overarching aims, timeline, audiences and style of activities.

1.2.1 Communication

The purpose of communication activities is to reach out to society, increasing the project visibility and demonstrating how the project advancements can contribute to tackle climate adaptation challenges. Communication activities will aim to promote the project and build awareness about the activities and developments, from the start to the completion of ASPECT. It is important that carefully constructed key messages are communicated at a suitable time and using appropriate language for targeted audiences. Multiple and diverse target audiences have been identified, such as policy-makers who are likely to require concise and non-technical communications and climate researchers who will require specific and technical content. A number of communication tools and channels will be used to inform these audiences, including (among others) the project website, social media, press releases, communication material (e.g., videos, infographics, sector-specific material), and news articles. A more detailed description of communication activities can be found in Table 2. Communication activities will be regularly monitored and evaluated to assess their impact.

1.2.2 Dissemination

The primary purpose of dissemination activities is to deliver relevant and tailored information on the outcomes of ASPECT to different target audiences, as well as to promote the project results and their uptake by different groups. Findings will be synthesised and shared to maximise the impact of the project, making sure they are available and accessible to those who can make best use of them. A host of different activities and materials will be prepared, including webinar series, case studies and paper briefings. All activities and outputs will be tailored to the specific target audience, overall aiming to be informative and clear, with the language and level of technical details appropriate to the target audience. The majority of dissemination activities will occur once results have been generated.

1.2.3 Exploitation

Exploitation activities aim to ensure the long-term impacts and legacy of the developments and products that are generated throughout the ASPECT project. The exploitation activities will aim to facilitate the external uptake of data and scientific advancements, while ensuring the project's legacy. A digital handbook and user training events will be developed to upskill users of climate information, while engagement with national meteorological services will maximise the uptake of ASPECT research across Europe. These activities will start later on in the project, as findings become available. The overarching aim is that exploitation activities will cascade and lead to ASPECT research informing business, government and organisational adaptation planning.

2 Target audiences

ASPECT will target a range of different audiences with various levels of expertise in using climate information and different requirements summarised in Figure 1. Within these groups, the project will span a range of key relevant socio-economic sectors (e.g., agriculture, finance, governance, energy and water), each with interests in different time-scales (seasonal, decadal and longer term) and importantly capture a wide range of spatial scales and regions. The main target audiences are identified below:

- **Climate research community**
We will share the developments in climate predictions with the scientific community to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration with researchers, and relevant projects and initiatives.
- **Decision makers in government, businesses and the third sector**
We will engage with decision makers, often non-experts in climate information use, to improve their awareness of the step change in the climate risk information available through ASPECT.
- **Adaptation practitioners**
We will share the enhanced predictions with adaptation practitioners and ensure they are understood and taken up by the adaptation community.
- **Climate forecasters and climate service providers**
We will share seamless information enhancements from ASPECT with the climate forecasters and services communities. This information will represent a step change in available actionable data, which forecasters and national meteorological services can provide their users and other stakeholders to inform adaptation and reduce vulnerability across a range of sectors in Europe.
- **General interest groups and wider society**
We will engage with non-experts and the wider public interested in climate information to enhance the reach of the project, raise awareness about climate information and promote the future uptake and use of this information by wider audiences.

Figure 1. ASPECT target audiences

2.1 Collaborations with existing initiatives and projects

The ASPECT project will build on previous knowledge, and aim to collaborate, share knowledge and exploit synergies with a range of existing national, European and international initiatives and projects, such as (but not limited to) those listed in Table 1. Scientific collaboration with new projects and programmes (such as WCRP Lighthouse activities and Destination Earth) will be sought out. In particular, ASPECT will engage with sister projects (e.g. Impetus4Change), as well as other EU projects (e.g. Climateurope2 and nextGEMs).

To aid scientific collaboration, and to enhance the cooperation and leadership, a number of named collaboration champions have been appointed from other WPs across ASPECT, who are already engaged in ongoing initiatives.

Table 1. Ongoing projects or initiatives relevant to ASPECT.

Relevant ongoing project or initiative	Brief description
Climateurope2	Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services of greater value to society, which will provide trustworthy, user-relevant and usable information.
Destination Earth (DestinE)	Destination Earth (DestinE) is an initiative to develop a highly accurate digital model of the Earth on a global scale.
EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change projects, such as CLIMAAX , Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change and Regions4Climate	The Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change focuses on supporting EU regions, cities and local authorities in their efforts to build resilience against the impacts of climate change.
Impetus4Change	Impetus4Change is improving near-term climate predictions for social transformation in regions and cities in Europe.
Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems (NextGEMS)	NextGEMS is building prototypes for a new generation of earth system models to advance science, guide policy, and inform applications to support the sustainable management of our planet.
World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) Lighthouse activities	The World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) has transdisciplinary lighthouse activities covering a range of topics the most relevant to ASPECT are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Digital Earths ● Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change
World Meteorological Organisation Global Annual to Decadal Climate Update (GADCU)	The GADCU is published annually (in May) and summarises the predicted future of the global climate over the next year and the next five years based on an ensemble of four global climate model predictions.

2.2 User engagement

User engagement (leading to co-development) is a core foundation of the project, taking place across various work packages. Throughout ASPECT, partnership with users will be central to establishing which climate metrics, impact relevant indicators or parts of the case studies might be insightful if scaled up for other users, geographical areas and sectors.

User engagement activities will be led by WP4 and WP5. WP7 will support user engagement by assisting in the preparation of appropriate materials to engage users, alongside providing dedicated resources for communication activities. Figure 2 summarises the interactions across WPs in ASPECT. WP4 will develop a deep understanding of the decision processes and requirements of a small set of case studies co-developed with ‘superusers’. WP5 will build a wider understanding of user needs interacting with a broader set of users through the multi-sector user forums, which will inform underpinning science decisions in WPs 1-3, facilitate scaling up of WP4 case study applications and the co-design of a broader climate service delivery system in WP6. For more information on the user forums, please refer to the Report on the annual multi-sector user forum (Deliverable 5.2).

Figure 2. Overarching structure and interactions between ASPECT work packages

ASPECT partners will provide training to the users of the research developed in the project, with support from WP7. The target audiences of these trainings will be national meteorological services, decision makers, and adaptation practitioners. The training will aim to allow the users to understand how individual predictions at different time scales, as well as the newly developed seamless climate predictions, have been produced and how to use them appropriately. The training offer will be tailored to the user requirements and level, based on user engagement work, which is currently underway, led by WP5.

3 Activities, products and materials

A comprehensive list of the CDE activities that are planned and underway are outlined in Table 2. Some of the activities have multiple and overlapping audiences or nature (CDE or user engagement); for simplicity, the most important of these are noted in the table below. This is a preliminary plan of activities and will be adapted according to the project needs. Any revisions will be included in the forthcoming CDEP updates (D7.2 in M18, D7.5 in M36, and D7.6 in M47). CDE materials will be available in English, while versions in other languages will be prepared when needed, prioritising those materials aimed to support user engagement activities.

Sections 3.1-3.3 provide more detail on the strategy and specific activities which are underway or soon to be implemented. Currently, other WPs are working to understand user needs and requirements, these findings will be used to develop user activities and materials such as the user training and the digital handbook, more details on these activities and materials will be available in future iterations of the CDEP.

Table 2. Planning of communication (C), dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and user engagement (UE) activities, including target audience, method/channel of communication and key performance indicator (KPI) targets for monitoring project impact.

Note that the due date is shown where relevant, and a date of M48 indicates an ongoing activity until the end of the project. The dates and status will be updated with the latest information in future deliverables.

Activity	Type of activity	Description and purpose	Target audience	KPI target	Due date	Status / Comments
Project website	C	The main communication hub for the project, aimed at those involved or interested in the project. It will provide the project description, latest news, events, reports, public deliverables, publications, and all communication material. A 'legacy' version of the website will be available for 5 years beyond the project end.	All	>500 visits over the lifetime of the project	M48	Ongoing Project website available: www.aspect-project.eu/
News articles on project website	C	Short news articles about ASPECT advances, activities and events written in accessible language with a focus on societal benefits.	All	>6 articles per year	M48	Ongoing
Social media	C	Regular posts on social media will be made to reach a wider community, increase the project visibility and engage stakeholders.	All	>200 total followers, >200 interactions	M48	Ongoing (Twitter , LinkedIn and Youtube accounts available)
Newsletters	C	Newsletters will be prepared and sent, with the frequency depending on the availability of project updates. The content will include upcoming events, key research highlights and opportunities for collaboration. Subscription to the newsletter has been promoted through the project website.	All, in particular ASPECT partners, superusers, and relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives	~2 per year depending on content, >50 subscribers to newsletter		Planning

Press releases/ briefings	C/D	Press releases and briefing materials will generate interest in the project, communicate about events and disseminate the results at local, regional and EU level. Disseminated on the project website, through social media and communication units of partners' organisations. The timing of press releases will aim to maximise impact.	Media, general public, all	>3 press releases		
Videos	C/D	Short videos to raise awareness and inform about key concepts and research conducted in the project to reach diverse audiences through social media and to be used in presentations.	All	≥6 short videos, >200 total views	M6 - M48	First video under development
Policy briefs	C/D	Aim to co-produce targeted two-page briefs that synthesise and translate information on a specific subject of particular relevance to decision- and policy-makers. The specific subject matter of each brief will be chosen to maximise the dissemination of key messages that are policy relevant. The briefs will be disseminated through the project communication channels and at relevant events.	Policymakers, adaptation practitioners, other projects and initiatives	≥3 policy briefs >10 policymakers reached		
Clustering activities	C/D	Collaborating and building synergies with relevant EU-funded projects, initiatives and clusters, including sister projects funded under the same call and other initiatives with partners' involvement (e.g., CORDEX, DestinE, EU Missions, Climateurope2).	Relevant project and initiatives	>5 collaborations	M48	Ongoing (interactions with Climateurope2, Impetus4Change, EERIE etc.)

Infographics	C/D	Visually striking and concise representation of key messages/findings from the project for specific audiences with the possibility to be integrated in other dissemination materials such as policy briefs, news articles and the ASPECT digital handbook.	All	>4 infographics >100 total engagements on social media		
Sector-specific dissemination material	C/D	Material tailored to the different sectors of interest of the project developed to facilitate engagement with users and present the application of the project's outcomes to a wider community (e.g. leaflet, poster). Disseminated through the project website and used in the multi-sector user forums.	Adaptation practitioners, non-scientist decision-makers	>100 views >3 sectors targeted		
Webinar series	C/D	Webinars targeting the different sectors tackled in the project, aimed to promote online discussions among participants (e.g., on scaling up project prototypes) and to build capacity. Webinar recordings will be made available on the project website.	Adaptation practitioners, non-scientist decision makers and advisors, operational forecasters and climate service providers, early career scientists and students	>50 total attendees		
Scientific publications	D	Sharing public project reports and publications in peer-reviewed journals will disseminate key project findings to the scientific community and climate adaptation community.	Climate research community, adaptation practitioners,	>10 publications		

			operational forecasters and climate service providers			
Paper briefings	D	Digested briefings of specific ASPECT papers and their implications will be disseminated through the project communication channels to ensure the key messages from the research also reach non-technical audiences.	Academia (beyond climate science community), adaptation practitioners, non-expert decision-makers	>5 paper briefings		
Case study booklet	D	Appealing document describing the co-production process followed for the development of the case studies and their application. Disseminated through the project communication channels.	Academia, adaptation practitioners, climate service providers	>50 interactions	M42	
Participation in relevant events	D	Presentations in relevant events that can help engaging with interested audiences while increasing the reach of project results, <i>e.g., European Geophysical Union (EGU), European Meteorological Society (EMS), European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA)</i>	Research community, adaptation practitioners, relevant EU-funded initiatives	>10 conference/workshop presentations		Participation in Climateurope2 webstival, and conferences (e.g. ECCA 2023)
Digital Handbook	C/D/E	A digital environment available through the project website to support stakeholders in applying and navigating the results of the project in diverse	Non-technical decision makers,	>50 views and interactions	M36	

		socio-economic sectors and contexts. The handbook will focus on climate information that can be obtained through the workflow (WP6), integrating examples from case studies (WP4), description of the science behind the climate information, and description of the production chain (WP1 and WP3) in a comprehensible language for non-scientist target audiences.	adaptation practitioners			
User training events (in collaboration with WP5)	D/E	Support a user training event, organised in collaboration with WP5 and other WPs, which will train new and existing users of climate predictions on the use of the delivery system developed in the project, building on foundations of the webinar series delivered earlier in the project	Adaptation practitioners, non-technical decision makers, national meteorological services, climate service providers	>25 participants	M42	
Engagement with national meteorological services	E	Support engagement with national meteorological services. Activities will include 1-2-1 consultations to understand their needs and challenges, involvement of the meteorological services in the design of the ASPECT delivery system, and tailored engagement to support and monitor the meteorological services as they begin to incorporate the new information and approaches into their own workflows, products and services.	National meteorological services	≥5 national met services engaged		

Multi-sector user forums	D/UE	Support annual multi-sector user forums to create a physical, virtual or hybrid space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users of climate information	Adaptation practitioners, non-technical decision makers and advisors	~200 participants in total		First user forum in two parts (Mar and Apr 2023) - >100 participants
Case studies	D/UE	Case studies co-developed with superusers from different socio-economic sectors to co-explore how different types of climate-related information (e.g. climate variables, indicators, risk indices, etc.) at various time-scales can help inform decisions for adaptation to climate change	Superusers, adaptation practitioners, climate service providers	≥5 case studies	M42	Planning

3.1 Website

A key component of the communication plan is a user-focused website that will be an important base where project information, updates and materials aimed at audiences with a range of background levels will be collected. Planning structure, production, and curations of all the content will fulfil the needs of users of the website, focussing on providing a clear user journey for different user types to enable them to access the most relevant information for them. A key component of the website will be the news section, where articles offer accessible and user-relevant updates of the latest project events and developments.

The website should be seen as a dynamic and constantly evolving environment, a space that changes as the project activities grow and is adapted to provide the best visibility for the different activities. Additionally, it has a visually appealing and user-friendly design, with a responsive layout that can adapt to different screen sizes. The website is optimised for search engines, ensuring that it is easily discoverable by interested parties. The site development took place during M1 and it is updated continuously. A legacy version of the website will be available for 5 years beyond the project end.

In its beta version, the website is organised into six sections plus the homepage. These sections will be updated and additional sections will be added progressively, when suitable materials are available, including: a “User area”, with resources for adaptation practitioners and decision makers; a “Resources” section, divided in the different types of communication and dissemination materials generated by the project (e.g. videos, scientific publications, digested briefings); a “Cluster” section will resume the interactions of ASPECT with other initiatives.

3.1.1 Homepage

The homepage is designed to highlight the vision and mission of the project with the latest information and content that shed light on the more relevant activities and outcomes related to ASPECT (Figure 3). The navigation menu includes social media links and gives access to all sections of the site. While scrolling down the page, the first section resumes in a nutshell the mission of the project, addressing to the project page for more details. The next sections include a larger description of ASPECT, addressing to the objectives page for more details. The third section offers space for the latest news and upcoming events (when relevant). Finally, the footer, which is present on all pages of the website, contains a banner for subscribing to the project’s mailing list, as well as official and formal information including the EU emblem, acknowledgement of the funding programme, and the Privacy Policy. Moreover, it is possible to access the internal project wiki through the footer.

Figure 3. Homepage of the project website

3.1.2 Project sections

Three pages give a general description of the project, including the aim, the goals and the objectives of ASPECT, as well as the consortium and the structure of the seven work packages (Figure 4).

ASPECT PROJECT OBJECTIVES PARTNERS NEWS EVENTS CONTACT

Project

Aim

ASPECT aims to improve the understanding of extreme weather events and their impact on society through the development of a new generation of user-driven metrics for the assessment of extreme weather events and their impact on society.

Goal

The goal is to improve the understanding of extreme weather events and their impact on society through the development of a new generation of user-driven metrics for the assessment of extreme weather events and their impact on society.

How

Through a baseline survey of information for the user-driven metrics, the project will develop a new generation of user-driven metrics for the assessment of extreme weather events and their impact on society.

Work packages

WP1 - Improving the predictive skills of weather-forecast models

WP2 - Improving knowledge for the preparation and adaptation

WP3 - Characterise and evaluate of weather-forecast information

WP4 - Co-developing user studies with users and existing forecasts

WP5 - Improving the usability of user-driven information for the assessment

WP6 - Data analysis

WP7 - Scientific co-validation, project management, communication, dissemination and exploitation of outcomes

ASPECT PROJECT OBJECTIVES PARTNERS NEWS EVENTS CONTACT

Objectives

#1 #2 #3 #4 #5 #6

Objective #1

Improving seasonal-to-decadal (S2D) forecasts, where forecasts are targeted on user-driven metrics

Objective #2

Planning new extended initialised forecasts up to 30 years ahead

Objective #3

Planning new approaches to data: the best forecasts on seasonal / 1-5 year / 5-30 year time-scales together

Objective #4

Designing and implementing new ways to extract high-resolution information on extremes

Objective #5

Exploring how users can get value from considering information on seasonal / 1-5 year / 5-30 year time-scales together to improve decision making

ASPECT PROJECT OBJECTIVES PARTNERS NEWS EVENTS CONTACT

Partners

Our partners

ASPECT is a project funded by the European Union. The project is coordinated by the Met Office. The project is supported by the following partners: University of Leeds, Met Office, University of Oxford, Raytheon Coorsell, SMHI, University of Paris.

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Figure 4. First version of the website project pages, which will be updated according to the project needs.

3.1.3 News and events

The News and Events sections are the most dynamic areas of the website (Figure 5). Here, updates on the project activities and events will be collated. These sections are populated as ASPECT activities develop during the project, to keep track of all initiatives related to the project or in which the project is involved. In the page dedicated to the events, the users can

find more information about the project upcoming and past events, such as webinars, workshops and conferences, as well as relevant climate services events organised by other external initiatives.

Figure 5. News and events pages of ASPECT website.

3.1.4 Contact

The page contains contact information to reach out to the project team for further information or queries. Visitors can write to hello.aspect@bsc.es, subscribe to the ASPECT newsletter and get in touch with the project coordinators.

3.2 Social media strategy

Social media is a useful platform to start dialogue with both engaged and new audiences. Social media channels are valuable platforms to reach a wide community, increase visibility and raise awareness, providing the opportunity for the project to reach new members of the target audiences. The scientific community and relevant research projects are also active on social media, meaning it can also be a useful platform to reach these groups. Policy makers and other target stakeholders can also be reached through social media via engaging non-technical messages.

Three social media channels have been identified as key platforms to engage with the project's target audiences (identified in Section 2): Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. Social media activities are planned internally, and all project partners encouraged to follow and engage with ASPECT's social media, sharing information about news, events, and other content covered by the project. Partners are reminded to retweet posts from their organisational and personal accounts, and repost LinkedIn page content with their networks to increase its reach and impact.

The ASPECT social media accounts were established at the beginning of the project, and the current aim is to progressively build a following. It is expected that the social media engagement and reach will grow over the lifetime of the project. Data on the followers and reach of the content will be gathered on a regular basis.

At the end of the project lifetime, the social media activity will cease. The accounts will remain for a further year to allow content to be accessed but a message will be posted to explain the project has ended and that the accounts are not monitored. The LinkedIn group will remain as a community lead space to allow continued interaction and collaboration into the future. As much content as possible will be hosted on the website to facilitate a legacy for 5 years from the project end.

3.2.1 Twitter strategy

An ASPECT Twitter account has been established to share news, results and key messages from the project. The Twitter page can be found using the handle [@ASPECT_project](https://twitter.com/ASPECT_project), and is linked in the project website and presentations.

The account is mainly maintained by the Met Office, with contributions by the BSC and other project partners, who are responsible for supporting the preparation of new content. The target audiences for Twitter include the scientific community, public and private organisations and businesses, related research projects, the media and the engaged general public.

The content published on the project's Twitter account will include the following:

- upcoming events organised by the project, or events in which ASPECT partners are participating
- project news, such as updates on the project activities, material and publications, all of which will be featured on the project website
- research findings synthesised into accessible outputs (such as infographics) for a non-technical audience
- ongoing and future research

- links to reports, info sheets and other material prepared in ASPECT
- videos summarising key messages or concepts from ASPECT research
- opportunities to collaborate with the project, such as the call for evidence, the opportunity to become a Super User or participate in user forums
- latest news related to climate adaptation (eg related to the IPCC, State of the Climate etc)
- relevant research findings or events from other relevant research projects or organisations

The aim is to post at least 1-2 times per week, including original content, as well as reposting relevant content from other research projects and initiatives and ASPECT scientists. ASPECT tweets will, where possible, tag other scientists, projects and organisations to maximise interactions. A number of handles and discoverable hashtags have been identified for use in regular tweets to expand reach and boost engagement, and are outlined in Table 3. When composing original content, the purpose, audience, and any overlap with other initiatives will be considered. This will inform the choice of hashtags and handles chosen to be included. If there are ASPECT events occurring, wherever possible, live tweets will be published during the event to spark conversations and enhance connections.

Table 3. Identified twitter handles and hashtags for regular use in original content.

Handles	Hashtags
@ASPECT_project	#ASPECTproject
@climateurope2	#climate
@IPCC_CH	#climatechange
@WMO	#climateadaptation
@HorizonEU	#adaptation
@cinea_eu	#climateresearch
@WCRP_climate	#HorizonEU
@I4C_eu	#resilience
@WCRP_Cordex	#userforum

3.2.2 LinkedIn Strategy

A LinkedIn public project page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/aspect-project/>) and a closed LinkedIn group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12779937/>) have been established for ASPECT. The public page aims to showcase ASPECT work and events, while the closed group aims to facilitate a collaborative space for project partners to build a community. Since the project group is more internally focused it won't be explored further in this document. The page is mainly managed by the Met Office using updates provided by project partners.

The LinkedIn page is externally facing with the intention of sharing events and showcasing the project to external professionals such as scientists and policy makers. The specific content that is planned for the page is listed below. The aim is to post at least on a monthly basis, with all project partners responsible for supporting the preparation of new content. Project partners who use LinkedIn are encouraged to share posts to capitalise on existing networks and contacts to disseminate important project deliverables and key messages.

Planned content for the externally facing LinkedIn page:

- upcoming events organised by the project, or events in which ASPECT partners are participating
- research findings synthesised into accessible outputs (such as infographics) for a non-technical audience
- ongoing and future research
- links to reports, info sheets and other materials prepared in ASPECT
- videos summarising key messages or concepts from the research
- opportunities to collaborate or input into research, such as the call for evidence or the opportunity to become a superuser or participate in user forums

3.2.3 YouTube strategy

A YouTube channel (@ASPECT_project, https://www.youtube.com/@ASPECT_project) has been set up for ASPECT which will host videos that summarise key research, outcomes and messages from the project as well as recordings of events. The videos will provide valuable and engaging content for sharing on social media, as well as material for training and presentations. The primary audience for the video content are stakeholders who are external to the project but likely to be interested in the outputs, such as decision makers in government, businesses and the third sector. The video content and language will therefore be accessible and engaging.

Six short bespoke videos will be produced for the project. The first of these videos will provide an introduction to ASPECT and is currently under development and aimed to be finalised in the next months. Videos will be named to maximise discoverability and engagement. The YouTube channel will also host recordings of events such as webinars and user forums to allow participants to refer back to information or stakeholders to engage if they were unable to attend events. Videos of longer recordings will be divided into chapters to enable users to easily navigate to the relevant content.

3.3 Visual identity

The ASPECT visual identity was created by a user experience expert at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, aiming to establish a recognisable and coherent ‘brand’ for the project that will be used in all project material. The design took into account basic accessibility requirements, such as selecting a colour-blind friendly palette. It includes the project logo, a colour palette, typefaces, and templates for various support materials, such as presentations and deliverables. Logos, templates and the visual identity guide are available in the ASPECT internal repository.

Figure 6. Project logo, for both white and dark backgrounds.

Figure 7. Colour palette used in ASPECT.

3.3.1 Branded templates

Branded presentation and deliverable or milestone templates are available for all ASPECT partners to use for all external communications. The templates use the ASPECT colour palette and logo and include formats for a range of content to ensure coherent visual identity across the project. These templates, along with the visual identity guide, can be found in the project’s internal repository (wiki).

4 Exploitation

Exploitation activities ensure the long-term impact and legacy of the developments and products that are generated in ASPECT. Exploitation measures and activities will aim to achieve data, science, and user legacy.

4.1 Supporting the data delivery system

A key long-term impact of the project will be the increased uptake of adaptation information across sectors, tiers of decision making and geographies. A key component of this legacy is the data delivery system, which will facilitate the automation and immediate application of datasets, developments, and workflows by users. A delivery system will be designed and implemented for the data and methods produced by ASPECT; this will enable scaling up the use of climate risk information on the 1 to 30-year time-scale beyond a few pilot studies, to become a mainstream tool in adaptation. The data delivery system development and implementation will draw on knowledge generated in all WPs, with a particular focus on WP5 (for evidence and approach to scaling up) and WP6 (delivery system), while WP7 will provide support in ensuring the data legacy of the project.

4.2 Digital handbook

A digital handbook will provide a digital environment to support stakeholders in navigating the data delivery system, exploiting their potential, and demonstrating any potential uses for which climate predictions are critical in realising adaptation options in several socio-economic sectors and contexts. The digital handbook will be built with multimedia and a flexible structure that will allow customised navigation for the different types of users who will be involved, with particular reference to decision-makers in the fields of policy, business, and civil society. The handbook will focus on climate information, insights and intelligence, which will be obtained from climate data through the developed workflows (WP6) and will also integrate examples from case studies (WP4), description of the science behind the climate information, and description of the production chain (WP1) in a comprehensible language for non-scientist target audiences. The digital handbook will also highlight links and connections between the project's results and European initiatives whose online resources are helpful for the exploitation and application of climate information for adaptation actions.

4.3 Uptake of scientific advances

The uptake of new scientific developments from ASPECT by other scientists and ongoing projects in climate prediction and adaptation is fundamental for the long-term impact of the project and seeding of future developments. Scientific publications are a key route to this, and these will be monitored, promoted through social media and the website, and digested into summaries of key findings and implications for a wider audience. The legacy of scientific developments will be supported by active collaboration during the project lifetime. A key component of the scientific exploitation strategy is to have nominated 'champions' for key initiatives (including CORDEX, Destination Earth and EU-missions) to create embedded links between ASPECT and these important leadership initiatives.

4.4 Supporting user training

A user training event, organised in collaboration with WP5 and other WPs, will deliver training on the use of the delivery system developed in the project, building on foundations of the webinar series delivered earlier in the project. Engagement with national meteorological services (NMS) will offer some of the best routes to further uptake of ASPECT outputs, drawing on the learning in the first year of the project (within WP5) and in consultation with the European Commission in order to maximise uptake, satisfy demand, and to achieve geographical coverage.

Particular activities will include detailed one-to-one consultations with the different NMS engaged to understand their needs and challenges, involvement of the met services in the design of the ASPECT delivery system, and tailored engagement to support and monitor the NMS as they begin to incorporate the new information and approaches into their own workflows, products and services.

4.5 Targeted engagement

WP7 will support the final component of scaling up the outputs of ASPECT to drive adaptation through focused engagement with several NMS. Several of these institutions are partners of the project or form part of the project's external international advisory board. The aim is to work closely with up to 10 additional national services across Europe in order to embed the ASPECT outputs into their service and to learn from them to improve the delivery system. The additional NMS will be selected to achieve an optimal geographical coverage and complement the superusers and user forums in WPs 4 and 5.

Furthermore, ASPECT partners will collaborate with, complement, and support relevant projects and initiatives. These partnerships will have a range of expected benefits including, running joint events to reach a larger audience, building on existing research and avoiding duplication, and sharing best practice.

5 Internal communication and interactions across the project

To ensure interactions among the different project partners and WPs, a number of communication channels have been established. These are detailed below.

5.1 Mailing lists

Mailing lists have been established for each WP to regularly communicate among project partners. To avoid communication overload for members not directly involved, each work package has its own mailing list, used for internal communication and organisation. All members of the ASPECT consortium have the opportunity to choose which mailing lists they would like to be included in; this has allowed partners to be included in relevant communications, which strengthens internal interactions.

5.2 Project wiki and internal reporting

ASPECT partners have access to an internal online wiki website. The wiki is a repository for project material and information, including project documents (e.g. deliverables, templates), information on reporting, partner contact details and a risk register. There is a dedicated CDE page with a link to a table for reporting events, activities or outputs that ASPECT partners organise, participate in or produce. The reporting table captures ASPECT presentations at events, scientific publications, activities and materials produced, user engagement, proposed events and clustering activities. This information will help to assess the ongoing level of engagement and outputs from ASPECT partners, and enable the progress towards impact and the respective KPIs to be monitored.

5.3 Meetings

Virtual WP7 meetings are held on a monthly basis, where partners design, execute, track, and assess the activities planned in WP7 and the CDEP. Regular meetings are also organised in several WPs, with representatives from other WPs attending these meetings where possible to facilitate effective collaboration and regular interactions across the project. In addition, to obtain an overview of the advances of different WPs and upcoming activities relevant to WP7, specific meetings between other WPs and WP7 are set up, as needed.

5.4 Acknowledgements

An acknowledgement of the project (logo), grant agreement number and European flag (emblem) should be used by partners in all material, presentations and activities related to ASPECT, following Article 17 of the Grant Agreement (*Communication, Dissemination and Visibility*). The following information is included in the ASPECT templates:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101081460. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

6 Evaluation and risks

6.1 Impact evaluation and CDEP updates

The first impact evaluation and update to the CDEP will take place in June 2024 (Deliverable 7.2) followed by a second evaluation in December 2025 (Deliverable 7.5). This will provide an opportunity to take stock of the progress of the first year and identify opportunities to improve. In November 2026, a final impact evaluation and communication plan of project legacy will be published (Deliverable 7.6).

There is a comprehensive list of the KPIs associated with each CDE activities detailed in Table 2 that have been allocated to achieve performance and impact. These activities and KPIs will be regularly reviewed and discussed according to the project needs, and their status will be updated in future CDEP deliverables, keeping track of the progress through internal monitoring documents. In addition, internal milestones have also been assigned to several CDE activities in the project to ensure continuous progress is achieved.

6.2 Potential barriers and risks

The potential barriers or risks to success of ASPECT CDE have been listed in Table 4. The potential likelihood and severity have been considered with proportionate mitigation measures proposed. The risks identified will be monitored and updated as the project develops and matures.

Table 4. Risks identified, related to CDE. High (H), Moderate (M) and Low (L) likelihood and severity are assigned to each risk.

Risk or barrier	Likelihood / severity	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Barriers to impact may occur if ASPECT encounters difficulties in engaging stakeholders and recruiting users, or users who do engage show reluctance to embrace new methods.	Likelihood: L Severity: H	ASPECT is aware of the need to build relationships and trust with users through the project lifetime. Building on existing relationships with users known to partners will help to demonstrate benefits and foster trust from new users. By developing a new, wider pool of active users, ASPECT will limit the risk of 'stakeholder fatigue'.
Barriers to collaboration may occur if results are insufficiently relevant, or if there is a lack of credible routes to key initiatives.	Likelihood: L Severity: H	ASPECT's approach of engaging with key initiatives through embedded champions will help initiate and maintain key links and enable us to maintain a two-way dialogue to ensure shared objectives are reached.
Upsurge in COVID infections requiring lockdown	Likelihood: L Severity: L	All partners are now experienced at working under local lockdown and limited travel situations, with protocols improving over the past few years. These protocols can be reintroduced as needed.